

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R4.3 Development of stress magnitude and strengths in different cases (side stress reduction by cooling and modifications in strengths by CO₂)

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1 INTRODUCTION

The rock mechanical strength data as reported in R4.2 and the corresponding Excel WP4-database. Here, all the geologic variability in key petrophysical parameters, geomechanical stiffness and strengths in the field are displayed. The stiffness and strength data are relevant when set in context with the field stresses and field stress variation. As explained in R4.2, and further exemplified in Fig. 1-1, the failure envelope describes the stress states at which irreversible rock failure occurs. Within these bounds the rock remains (more or less) intact. The purpose of this report is to describe how the stress state is varied when cooling and re-pressurization occurs, to provide the direct observations of how long-term exposure of CO₂ change the ultrasonic stiffness, and how these measurements are correlated to mechanical strength. As such, an evaluation of rock strength weakening upon CO₂ exposure can be made.

This analysis is performed in qp space. The advantage with that is that, on the contrary of $\tau\sigma$ -space (see R4.2) the field stresses are represented with a point in this diagram. Now, since there is no direct field observations the field stress estimates vary significantly depending on the method used – the principal stresses are uncertain. Direct calculations from weight and uni-axial strain assumption, and extrapolation from nearby fields were performed to make this analysis. It is further assumed in the analysis that the two lowest Earth stresses are the same, i.e. $s_2 = s_3$, i.e. we make a 2D evaluation. This is done for two reasons; to be conservative in our assessment of reservoir stability, and more importantly, when there is lack of direct data it does not add any credibility to the presented results to make a more mathematically detailed evaluation when input parameters are unknown. As such, the qp -space relies on the following calculation of the two axes where,

$$q = s_1 - s_3, \text{ and } p = \frac{s_1 + s_3}{2} - \alpha_B P_f,$$

where s_1 and s_3 is the vertical and side stress, respectively, α_B is Biot coefficient and P_f is the pore pressure.

During operation of the field the effective stresses in the reservoir changes due to pore pressure build-up and cooling by the injection of CO₂. This assessment starts at pristine reservoir pressure, assuming hydrostatic gradient of the fluids involved. During depletion, i.e. pore pressure draw down, the mean effective stresses p is increased, bringing the stress data to the right of the initial green cloud in Fig. 1-1. When cold CO₂ is re-injected into the reservoir the side stress reduces due to thermal contraction of the rocks and since the reservoir sides are held in-place, a thermo-elastic stress reduction occurs. In that case q increases while p reduces, thus bringing the stress data toward failure limit (yellow). This report describes the theoretical foundation and reports the laboratory derived input data needed to make this analysis.

Given the inherent uncertainty in the reservoir field stress data, and the input data used to determine the thermo-elastic coupling, we made a Monte Carlo analysis where we estimate mechanical stability for each realization of the variable data as described in this report.

CO₂ and brines can react chemically with the reservoir rock-types in the field. A strength test of a given sample can only be done once. To assess whether geochemical alterations (determined in WP5) lead to mechanical weakening, the dynamic stiffnesses from ultrasonic velocity measurements were evaluated before and after CO₂ exposure. This signal, combined with

correlations between ultrasonic stiffness and mechanical strength, is used to provide quantitative insights mechanical stability over time.

These are fundamental concepts needed to understand the relation between the WP4 work and its association with the other work packages in the CO₂-SPICER project. WP4 will, in Milestone M4.1, report the geomechanical constraints to WP3 – modelling, and, in addition, works with WP6 on risk characterization to make sure the injected CO₂ remains underground, and with WP8 on determining which scenarios that are attainable within the geomechanical constraints.

Fig. 1-1: qp effective stress and failure plot for well ZA4A (where samples were used for UCS, triaxial and tensile strength tests). Circles represent stresses and pore pressures as drawn from a probability distribution using Monte Carlo analysis. The initial stress and pressure configuration is shown in green, the re-pressured stress-state in grey, the cooled down reservoir in blue, and the combination of cooling and re-pressurization in yellow. The tensile failure stress is displayed by green line, while the dashed line represents the Mohr Coulomb failure line from UCS and 3-axial tests. The mathematical basis and the input of this analysis are described in this report.

2 FIELD STRESS ASSESSMENT

There are no direct observations of what the principal stresses and stress directions are in the field. As such, we have been obliged to search for other ways to determine these stresses, as the evaluation of rock strength is only relevant when field stresses are known. These measurements are subject to uncertainty, so that the results will be given with error bands.

2.1 Extrapolation from nearby fields

Stress as function of depth were measured in three sites located east of Ostrava, while our injection site is situated near Brno, around 140 km away (Fig. 2-1 and Tab. 2-1). The principal stresses were measured at 700-900 meter depths. As can be seen in Fig 2-2, the stresses increase with depth, and by fitting a straight line (that encapsulates 75% of the measurements) the upper and lower bonds of the projected stresses at depth of the reservoir at 1724 m. These are $s_1 = 42.3 \pm 0.8$ MPa and $s_3 = 22.9 \pm 1.9$ MPa.

Fig. 2-1: Map of the injection site and where the stresses are measured.

Tab. 2-1: Three Czech Republic fields where s_1 , s_2 , and s_3 were measured.

Latitude	Longitude	Type	Locality	Country
49.81747	18.54852	HFG	CSM colliery	Czech Republic
49.82861	18.44605	HFG	Lazy colliery	Czech Republic
49.84815	18.45723	HFG	Doubrava colliery	Czech Republic

Fig. 2-2: Upper and lower curves fitted to the stress measurements that were used to the extrapolated stresses.

2.2 Calculating from weight of overburden and uni-axial strain

In reservoir systems one may assume the vertical stress to be largest. Based on an assessment of the overburden rock types, an overall density of $2300 \pm 50 \text{ kg/m}^3$ can be attained. At 1724 m depth a vertical stress of $s_1 = 38.9 \pm 0.8 \text{ MPa}$ can be obtained. Given uni-axial strain assumption, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.35, a horizontal stress of $s_3 = \frac{s_1 \nu}{1-\nu} = 20.0 \pm 0.6 \text{ MPa}$. The extrapolated stresses (square boxes) and estimated from overburden weight and Poisson's ratio (diamonds) are displayed in Fig. 2-3.

Fig. 2-3: Field stresses in circle, and the extrapolated and estimated stresses displayed. The red line represents the hydrostatic gradient.

In all, the field stresses as obtained above were used further in our analysis of stability in qp space. The values of initial pore pressure p_f and stresses s_1 and s_3 obtained and used in the analysis are shown in Tab. 2-2.

Tab. 2-2: Table of field stresses and pristine pore pressure to be used to assess stability of the core samples when exposed to pressure variation and cooling.

	s_1 [MPa]	s_3 [MPa]	P_f [MPa] (hydrostat)
Overburden and uni-axial strain	38.9 ± 0.8	20.0 ± 0.6	17.2 ± 1
Extrapolation of nearby fields	42.3 ± 0.8	22.9 ± 1.9	17.2 ± 1
Chosen for the analysis	40 ± 1.0	22 ± 2	17.2 ± 1

3 IMPACT OF COOLING AND REPRESSURIZATION

Here, we describe the mathematical basis for assessing how cooling and repressurization affects the reservoir stresses. At the same time, we report the experimental parameters that enter the evaluation. We further describe the Monte Carlo analysis tool that draws a random number from the uncertain data of the variable stresses/pressures. For each realization the stress is subject to change as the reservoir cools down and repressurizes during injection takes place.

3.1 Effective stress and pore pressure variation

The effective stress concept, as described by Terzaghi principle, quantifies the equivalence of changing the pore pressure and the externally imposed tectonic stresses. Further, Biot found that from data collapse of different rock-types only a fraction of the pore pressure was relevant to describe rock deformation. This work gave him his own coefficient named after him, the Biot's coefficient α_B , that depends on lithology. The Biot's coefficient is linked to how neighbouring grains are held together in a porous rock (intergranular cementation and pressure solution mechanisms, etc.). The Biot's coefficient can be determined in several ways, one of which uses the following relation (see Equation 1.169 in Fjær et al. 2008),

$$\alpha_B = 1 - \frac{C_{sol}}{C_{fr}} = 1 - \frac{K_{fr}}{K_{sol}}$$

The solid compressibility ($C_{sol} = 1/K_{sol}$), i.e. the weighted average compressibility of the mineralogy that makes up the rock, were obtained from results of the Quant Reitveld method (X-ray diffraction analysis) in WP5. A value of $K_{sol} = 94$ GPa was used. The framework modulus (rock sample itself), i.e. the bulk modulus, was estimated from ultrasonic velocity measurements of v_p and v_s (see R4.2). For the Vranovice dolomite reservoir rocks, the Biot's coefficient is shown in Fig. 3-1: as function of porosity (for the samples with porosity and sound velocity determined). A value of 0.85 ± 0.08 was obtained. The Biot's coefficient dictates how pore pressure variations lead to changes in p .

Fig. 3-1: Biot's coefficient as function of sample porosity.

3.2 Side stress reduced by cooling

Assuming the reservoir rock is held together at all sides, and that the overburden weight remains the same, a uniaxial assumption is valid. In this case, considering a 2D scenario, that is a conservative estimate, the following thermoelastic coupling coefficient between the change in temperature ΔT and the side stress Δs_3 apply (Voake et al., 2019ab),

$$\Delta s_3 = \frac{E \alpha_T}{1 - \nu} \Delta T$$

where the Young's stiffness modulus E , Poisson's ratio ν and the thermal expansion coefficient α_T are experimentally derived parameters with upper and lower bounds as shown in the following sub-sections.

Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio were estimated from ultrasonic velocity measurements via:

$$E_{dyn} = \rho v_s^2 \frac{3v_p^2 - 4v_s^2}{v_p^2 - v_s^2}$$

$$\nu_{dyn} = \frac{v_p^2 - 2v_s^2}{2(v_p^2 - v_s^2)}$$

For the samples where porosity was measured on the same sample as sound velocity (14 samples), the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio are plotted in Fig. 3-2 and 3-3. As can be seen, porosity is important for the Young's modulus. When extrapolating to 10% porosity, which is in the range of what is measured in the field, a more realistic Young's modulus can be obtained. The Reuss lower bound has been fitted to the laboratory data (green squares) and extrapolated to 10% porosity (green line in Fig. 3-2), where a value of 6.25 MPa was given.

Poisson's ratio is to a lesser extent controlled by porosity, see Fig. 3-3. All 48 reservoir samples were subject to sound velocity tests, and a histogram of all these tests is displayed in Fig. 3-4. From the histogram The Poisson's ratio is given with an average and standard deviation by $\nu = 0.35 \pm 0.05$.

Fig. 3-2: Young's modulus as function of porosity (14 samples).

Fig. 3-3: Poisson's ratio as function of porosity.

Fig. 3-4: Histogram of Vranovice dolomite Poisson's ratio from sound velocity. The number of instances are counted with steps in Poisson's ratio of 0.03 (box width).

The bulk modulus values were obtained from the Coreval 700 confining pressure cycle tests. Here, the bulk stiffness was obtained from measurement of the pore volume, and estimated rock volume, for varying confining stresses. Five examples of such tests are displayed in Fig. 3-5. By fitting a straight line to all 15 samples (five examples displayed in Fig. 3-5) the bulk modulus can be estimated, and for each sample the bulk modulus can be plotted with porosity along the x-axis in Fig. 3-6.

Fig. 3-5: Bulk volume strain as function of confining pressure for five reservoir samples with porosity ranging from 0.76 to 4.84 %.

Coreval 700. Stiffness poro-perm (15 smpl)

Fig. 3-6: Bulk modulus from Coreval 700 measurements.

By using $\nu = 0.35$, we may estimate the Young's modulus (Table 1 in Fjær et al., 2008), from the Poisson's ratio and bulk modulus using equation:

$$E = 3K(1 - 2\nu)$$

In Fig. 3-7, the estimated Young's modulus from Coreval 700 is plotted as function of porosity. As can be seen, porosity is the controlling parameter.

These result are not directly applicable to the larger scale reservoir perspective. Here, an average porosity, as reported by WP3, exceeds all the samples tested (values around 10% has been reported). How can we assign an appropriate stiffness of the reservoir? We have chosen a conservative estimate to take the Young's modulus at 5% porosity, i.e. 3 GPa, as be seen as the stippled line ("Extrapol") in Fig. 3-7. This is a conservative estimate, on the reservoir scale.

Coreval 700. Poro-perm analysis (15 smpl)

Fig. 3-7: Young's modulus estimated from bulk volume measurements and Poisson's ratio of 0.35. Here, Young's modulus is plotted as function of measured porosity.

The thermal expansion coefficient α_T of these rocks was determined from direct length measurements of four cores at 20 and 100°C. Their lengths were measured using a micrometer screwing device, pressing the sample between two even surfaces. From these measurements the thermal expansion coefficient was estimated using:

$$\alpha_T = 3 \frac{L_{100^\circ\text{C}} - L_{20^\circ\text{C}}}{L_{20^\circ\text{C}}} \frac{1}{\Delta T}$$

Tab. 3-1: Experimental determination of thermal expansion coefficient for three reservoir rocks and Mikulov marls seal

Sample ID	Box ID	L _{20°C} (mm)	L _{100°C} (mm)	α (K ⁻¹)	Lithostratigraphy	Type
UH11_c4_b3_d	UH11_c4_b3	19.64	20.63	1.89E-03	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir
UH3_c4_b6_a	UH3_c4_b6	28.94	28.99	6.48E-05	Mikulov Fm.	Seal
ZA4A_c1_b3_b	ZA4A_c1_b3	21.15	21.16	1.77E-05	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir
ZA4A_c1_b3_c	ZA4A_c1_b3	21.78	21.82	6.89E-05	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir

The values for Vranovice Fm. range from 1.8 to 6.9 · 10⁻⁵ K⁻¹. These measurements are difficult to perform, so that in order to gain confidence in which numbers to choose we performed a literature survey of already published data.

Table A.5 in Fjær et al. (2008) shows values of thermal expansion coefficients from 2 to 3 · 10⁻⁵ K⁻¹ for calcite. Similarly, Harvey (1967) reports that for dolomitic rocks the thermal expansion coefficient ranges from 4.3 to 5.5 · 10⁻⁶ F⁻¹. When converted to Kelvin (multiply by 9/5), this equates to ranges from 0.77 to 0.99 · 10⁻⁵ K⁻¹. Luque et al. (2011) provide direct measurements of calcitic and dolomitic marbles with results ranging

from 0.8 to $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$. Further, considering different thermal expansion coefficients of limestones, as reviewed in table 1 in T. Voake's PhD-thesis (2019), values range from 0.3 to $0.9 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

As such, compared to other reported data the experimental results are high when compared to the above mentioned measurements. It is therefore, based on the literature survey, assumed a volumetric thermal expansion coefficient in the range $\in [1 \cdot 10^{-5}, 1.8 \cdot 10^{-5}] \text{ K}^{-1}$.

When collecting all results of Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and thermal expansion coefficient, and their upper and lower values, we can define the upper and lower bounds of the thermo-elastic coupling coefficient. This is shown in Tab. 3-2. For each degree the temperature is reduced, the corresponding change in side stress is 1.1+/-0.7 bar.

Tab. 3-2: Thermo-elastic coupling coefficient linking cooling to side stress reduction. The values were discussed above.

	Lower	Upper	Average	Delta
Thermal expansion coeff. [K^{-1}]	1.00E-05	1.80E-05	1.40E-05	4.00E-06
Young's modulus [MPa]	3.00E+03	6.25E+03	4.63E+03	1.63E+03
Poisson's ratio	0.300	0.400	0.350	0.050
Thermal-stress coupling coeff. [MPa, K^{-1}]	0.043	0.188	0.115	0.072

4 MONTE CARLO ANALYSIS OF RESERVOIR STABILITY

Monte Carlo analysis tools are used to determine the mechanical stability when cooling and re-pressurization occurs due to the injection of cold CO_2 . The analysis is performed for varying reservoir temperatures and pore pressures. In each realization values were drawn from the probability distribution of stress, pore pressure, and thermo-elastic coupling coefficient and plotted in qp -space with the failure envelope. When the effective stresses are inside the failure envelope, the situation is deemed 'stable', and if the stress plots above the failure envelope it is 'unstable'. For each temperature and pore pressure 10 000 realizations were performed. This was used to calculate the number of unstable realizations, i.e. the probability of failure.

The initial side stress, pore pressure, Biot's coefficient and the thermo-elastic coupling coefficient were varied within input boundaries described above in Tab. -2 and Tab. 3-2:, respectively. For each realization, the Monte Carlo software sampled from a uniform ('flat'/'squared') distribution of the quantity, bounded by the upper and lower estimate as shown in these tables. A uniform distribution was assumed to be conservative in our assessment, and since the number of data points is too small to claim a well-defined average, i.e. we could not claim that a single value within the bound were more probable than the others.

For each realization the software samples randomly the initial stresses, Biot's coefficient and pore pressure, and thermo-elastic coupling coefficient within the given

bounds (uniform distribution). This enables a plot of the stresses positioned in qp -space at the pristine conditions, i.e. 52 °C and 17.2 MPa pore pressure, as green circles in Fig. 4-1 to Fig. 4-3). The analysis rests on the assumption that the pressure depletion down to 120 bar (today's condition, and further down) does not lead to irreversible mechanical changes in the rocks. R4.2 report display hydrostatic confining pressure cycles data, where the stress-strain paths during loading and unloading overlap, i.e. supporting this assumption.

In Fig. 4-1 to 4-3 the impact of cooling are displayed as blue circles while the impact of re-pressurization are displayed as grey, and the combined effect of cooling and re-pressurization are displayed as yellow circles. All cases are evaluated relative to the failure envelopes and the number of unstable instances, i.e. the number of yellow circles above the failure envelope, are calculated. This procedure is done for a range of pore pressures and reservoir temperatures. Three examples are shown in Fig 4-1, Fig. 4-2, and Fig. 4-3 where re-pressurization by 2, 5, 8 MPa (to 19.2, 23.2 and 25.2 MPa pore pressure), and cooling by -5, -20 and -30 °C (to reservoir temperature of 47, 32, 22 °C) are displayed, respectively.

In such a way we are able to determine the number of instances at which failure occurs for any combination of pore pressure and reservoir temperature. The evaluation were done for both intact rocks, using tensile strength and shear failure displayed as green line and black dashed line, respectively, and for re-opening of pre-existing fractures with its surface normal parallel to s_3 (orange line).

Fig. 4-1: qp effective stress and failure plot for well ZA4A. Pristine stress levels correspond to green circles; the yellow circles display the stress state after cooling the reservoir to 47 °C and increasing the pore pressure to 19.2 MPa.

Fig. 4-2: qp effective stress and failure plot for well ZA4A. The yellow circles represent the stress state when the reservoir is cooled to 32 °C and re-pressurized to 22.2 MPa.

Fig. 4-3: qp effective stress and failure plot for well ZA4A. Stresses at 30 °C cooling and re-pressurization to 25.2 MPa. Several of the yellow cases are unstable.

The Monte Carlo calculations were performed in Excel („QP-Error-failure-envelope.xls“), using data tables. This enables us to count the number of unstable events as function of systematic variation in pore pressure and temperature. This also enables us to provide systematic variation as displayed in Fig. 4-4. This analysis is the core of the handover to WP3 milestone M4.1, answering the question “what are the geomechanical limits found in WP4 to the modelled injection programme.

Fig. 4-4: Probability of failure at varying pore pressure and reservoir temperature.

5 MECHANICAL IMPACT OF CO₂ EXPOSURE AT INSITU CONDITIONS

The purpose here has been to establish if the strength of the rocks would be subject to change upon CO₂ interaction. At the same time ultrasonic stiffness is non-destructive enabling measurements of sound velocity both before and after CO₂ exposure.

Samples were exposed to CO₂ over 6 months in reaction cabinets at VSB Ostrava as a part of the work conducted in WP5 (reservoir brine composition). The dynamic stiffness using ultrasonic velocity were established for five of these samples before and after being exposed to CO₂. This data is shown in Tab. 5-1, where the also the dynamic stiffness parameters of Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus are estimated. In three reservoir samples (from the sample overview provided by WP1) the Young's modulus reduced to 53, 56 and 90% of the value before CO₂ exposure (average 66%), while one of the four samples (well UH11, core 4 and box 3¹) we observed a 51% increase in Young's modulus.

Thus, it seems, with great deal of uncertainty that the sound velocity may reduce due to the chemical interaction between the reservoir rock and CO₂/brine mixture at in-situ conditions. Now, since a sample can only be crushed once we take advantage of the data

¹ The UH11-well is placed outside / north of the reservoir structure. The sample UH11_c4_b3 is a reservoir carbonate rock, although its stratigraphic position is partly unclear (based on microfacial analyses). The results of these samples are thus omitted from the geomechanical analysis.

base described in R4.2 to study correlations between mechanical strength and stiffness. In Fig. 5-1, the correlation between tensile strength of both seals and reservoir rocks is shown. As can be seen, the sealing samples have an overall higher tensile strength than the reservoir rock. And, there is a weak correlation between the ultrasonic stiffness along the x-axis and the measured tensile strength (Brazilian tests) on the y-axis. If we consider an example of 66% reduction in elastic stiffness applied to reservoir (blue circles) this leads to an overall reduction in tensile strength by 10.7%, to a tensile strength of 89.3% of the value before CO₂ exposure (see arrow in Fig. 5-1).

The same analysis, to evaluate the relation between reduction in stiffness and strength, is performed for unconfined compressive strengths and ultrasonic tests. Here, we have five reservoir samples to draw upon as shown in Fig. 5-2 (blue circles). In this case, the data analysis shows that a reduction in elastic stiffness to 66% of the value before CO₂ exposure (from e.g. 40 to 26.2 GPa) would lead to a reduction in unconfined compressive strength from 86.8 to 52.9 MPa (see black arrow in Fig. 5-2), i.e. a reduction by 39%, that is the unconfined compressive strength after CO₂ exposure is reduced to 61% of the value before exposure.

When using the triaxial tests we have only three reservoir samples with complete failure strength and ultrasonic stiffness data. Fig. 5-3 display the largest axial principal stress at which the samples fail when kept at a constant side stress of 7 MPa. Along the x-axis the Young's modulus is plotted. A reduction in Young's modulus to 66% of the value before CO₂ exposure leads (from e.g. 45 to 29.7 GPa) lead to a reduction in the axial stress at failure from 158 to 120 MPa, i.e. a reduction to 75.8% of the value before CO₂ exposure.

There are in all reasons to believe there the geomechanical properties are up to change when exposed to CO₂.

The method applied here are subject to inherent uncertainty. In the further work towards publication, we will quantify the certainty at which conclusions can be drawn from uncertain and small data sets. There are further large uncertainties in both the geological sampling procedure as we can never be certain that the rock samples selected for analysis are representative of the overall reservoir performance. Further on, there are inherent uncertainties in the quantities that are measured.

Tab. 5-1. Ultrasonic velocities for v_p and v_s measured on five samples before and after CO₂ exposure. The Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus were calculated. UH11-well is placed north of the reservoir, and even though the sample is a carbonate rock it is considered an analogue to the reservoir.

Sample ID	Age	Lithostratigraphy	Type	Before				After CO2 exposure				Change
				Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	Vp, km/s	Vs, km/s	nu, 1	E, GPa	Youngs mod.
UH11_c4_b3_d	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. Kurdějov (Ernstbrunn Fm?)	Reservoir - possible analogue	6.67	2.28	0.43	32.71	6.09	2.87	0.36	49.23	151 %
ZA3_c1_b3_a	Paleogene	Žarošice Mb.	Seal	5.68	3.31	0.24	59.83	5.69	2.92	0.32	49.53	83 %
ZA6A_c1_b4_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	4.79	2.45	0.32	41.22	3.35	1.80	0.30	21.77	53 %
ZA4A_c3_b3_c	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm.	Reservoir	2.11	0.82	0.41	4.93	1.86	0.61	0.44	2.77	56 %
ZA4A_c4_b2_b	Upper Jurassic	Vranovice Fm. (Nikolčice Fm.)	Reservoir	3.14	1.64	0.31	17.70	2.65	1.63	0.19	15.93	90 %

Fig. 5-1. Correlation between tensile strength of all samples and the associated dynamic Young's modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements of v_p and v_s . Reservoir rock samples plotted in blue circles and seals in orange. Reduced modulus reduces T_0 .

Fig. 5-2. Correlation between measurements of unconfined compressive strength and the dynamic Young’s modulus estimated from ultrasonic measurements. A reduction in stiffness to 66% of the value before exposed to CO₂ lead to a corresponding reduction in UCS, as shown by the arrow. Reservoir rocks are displayed in blue circles, while the seals in orange.

Fig. 5-3. Correlation between ultrasonic dynamic stiffness and measured axial principal strength in triaxial tests. The side stress were kept at 7 MPa and the sample was loaded axially to failure (y-axis). Three samples. An elastic modulus reduced to 66% of the initial value reduce the value of s_1 , as displayed by the arrow.

6 CONCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD

This report describes the fundamental basis of how cooling and re-pressurization lead to stress changes in a reservoir with constant width and overburden weight. The report combines rock mechanical strength data with stiffness data measured by project partner VSB (Ostrava, Czech Republic). The purpose is to evaluate the mechanical stability as cooling and re-pressurization shifts the stresses towards the failure line. R4.2 provides complete overview of the data set obtained in WP4, while this report focuses on how to utilize the data to make sure the injected CO₂ remains underground.

The methods and data reported will be further used to prepare the hand-over of the geomechanical constraints to the injection programme from WP4 to WP3, which corresponds to Milestone 4.1 (M4.1). In the M4.1 document, a more detailed overview of all Monte Carlo runs that were developed together with the WP3 team is provided. Moreover, the work-flow established will be used for a more detailed risk analysis together with the WP6 team.

Exposing reservoir rock samples to CO₂ in the reaction cabinet at in-situ conditions led to a reduction in dynamic Young's modulus for all three examples. Via using the observed correlations between dynamic modulus and between mechanical strength tests we can quantify the geomechanical implication of the chemical reactions. Thus far, the presented data supports the hypothesis that chemical reaction changes the rock strength. However, the data is subject to great uncertainty, and we only have access to limited number of tests. Therefore, a more detailed quantification tool must be employed to evaluate uncertainty propagation in hypothesis testing will be provided in the peer review publications due 2024 (scattered and limited data sets).

The reservoir cooling and re-pressurization has implications for the reservoir injection programme, including development of the top surface installations. To what degree is pre-conditioning by warming up the injected CO₂ needed to increase the injection capacity? This a trade-off for further scenario developments in WP8. The temperature that will manifest itself in the reservoir will rely on using the measurements of thermal heat capacity of the relevant rock types (R4.2) as the temperature of the injected CO₂ will equilibrate with oil, formation water and gas (depending upon the injection scenarios to be assessed) and the rocks. Near-well zones will over time end up with a temperature equal to the injected CO₂ as the well will cool down. A more detailed prediction of the temperature fronts that will migrate through the reservoir is subject to flow simulations.

The results are collected, and plots are made in a series of Excel worksheets that are stored in the project geodatabase. They are titled:

- a) „WP4_QP-errorFailureEnvelope.xls“ - calculates stresses as function of pore pressure and temperature and performs the Monte Carlo analysis with variable/uncertain input data. This is focused on qp-space;
- b) „Stress_database.xls“ - displays the stress data base as collected in WP4 to assess what the reservoir stresses can be
- c) „Side-stress-calc-thermal-stresses.xls“ - a tool to plot the relation between reservoir temperature and re-pressurization using Mohr's circles and tau/sigma space.
- d) „2022-12-09-MASTER_WP4-SPICER.xls“- contains a complete overview of all experimental results performed in WP4

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